

Regression Rates of Non-liquefying Fuels in a Hybrid Rocket Engine at Atmospheric Pressure

Chen Szu Heng¹, Emmy Cai², Shahzaib Abedin³, Liam Novak⁴, Ian Meservey⁵

¹American International University Bangladesh, chaldwinben@gmail.com

²American International University Bangladesh, zcui233@gmail.com

Author Correspondence: Baridhara Road 10 Flat 1B, Dhaka, Bangladesh, +8801847228234,
chaldwinben@gmail.com

Abstract

Hybrid rocket propulsion systems offer many advantages including throttling capabilities and safety. This study investigates the regression rates of non-liquefying fuels in hybrid rocket engines operating under atmospheric pressure conditions with the purpose to investigate the effects of chamber pressure and establishing a pure baseline database. Traditional polymeric fuels were the main focus of the study. The three fuels studied were high density polyethylene (HDPE), polypropylene (PP), and polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA). Regression rates were measured and the a and n experimental constants were obtained. Regression rate correction was also applied. A comparative analysis was performed, comparing the findings with existing literature data. Discrepancies were observed, highlighting the influence of external factors and chamber pressure on regression rates. The findings show discrepancy between the regression rates of fuels under different chamber pressures when compared to other studies, providing valuable insights for fuel selection and mission design. Moreover, the study emphasizes the importance of establishing pure regression rate databases to facilitate accurate comparisons and optimize the performance of hybrid rocket engines.

Keywords: Hybrid propulsion, rocket, regression rate, non-liquefying fuel, chamber pressure

1. Introduction

1.1 Hybrid Overview

Chemical rocket propulsion systems are typically classified into three categories: solid, liquid, and hybrid. Whereas solid and liquid utilizes both the fuel and oxidizer in their corresponding states, hybrids feature a system commonly consisting of a solid fuel with a circular port and a liquid/gaseous oxidizer moving through it (Marquardt & Majdalani, 2019). As of now, the two main classifications of hybrid fuel have been divided into non-liquefying and liquefying. Liquefying fuels like paraffin wax differ in that when in the process of combustion, a liquid layer is formed on the fuel grain surface where droplets of fuel become entrained in the gas stream (Karabeyoglu *et al.*, 2001).

The hybrid system is distinctively different from both other systems, and offers many advantages which have on many occasions made it an attractive alternative. These advantages include safety, simplified throttling, lower operational cost, and propellant composition flexibility (Altman & Holzman, 2007).

Whereas hybrid fuel can be manufactured, stored, then inserted into the combustion chamber without risks of explosion, pre-mixed mixture of solid propellants is prone to accidental ignition which has often been catastrophic given that the combustion process cannot be stopped. Unlike liquids, hybrid systems do not have to maintain synchronized rates of fuel and oxidizer when throttling the engine. The fuel grain also is able to act as an absorbent for stress from chamber pressure and heat from combustion. Therefore, hybrid systems can have fewer moving parts which gives rise to a lower operational cost (Altman & Holzman, 2007).

Hybrid engines also have greater propellant versatility with greater selections of fuel (non-liquefying and liquefying), additives and oxidizer. The fuel is then able to be stored in a denser form compared to liquid. Furthermore, the simple hybrid systems allow adjustments of the fuel grain geometry in order to increase the performance of the engine. In the past, these have included the use of helical ports by Whitmore, Walker, Merkley, and Sobbi, which aims to reduce the blowing effect through the introduction of a centrifugal force causing an increase in convective heat transfer effectiveness (Whitmore *et al.*, 2015). Other means of increasing regression rates of a hybrid rocket engine has been through the implementation of swirling injectors such as ones used in the study by C.P. Kumar and A. Kumar (Kumar & Kumar, 2013).

Despite the advantages hybrids may offer, they are not commercially widespread due to certain shortcomings, namely low regression rate, which makes them inapplicable at large scales and for space operations. Notably, hybrids have regression rates typically 25% lower than those of solids under the same testing conditions (Whitmore *et al.*, 2015). Due to this low regression rate, many consequences arise such as a high aspect ratio which leads to poor volumetric efficiency and a low bulk density, which often prompts designers to use multiport designs such as ones experimented by Ahn, Kang, Lee, Yun, and Kwon (Ahn *et al.*, 2018). Meanwhile, the structure of hybrid engines introduces dynamical phenomena such as the shift of oxidizer-to-fuel ratio over time (O/F shift), which may call for more complex designs such as time-variable oxidizer injectors to compensate (Karabeyoglu *et al.*, 2014). The combustion process is also largely determined by dynamical processes in the boundary layer, which has led to a lack of applicable theoretical models across different scales, fuels and oxidizers, even with the introduction of improved computer simulations.

While recent developments with liquefying fuels have reduced many of the aforementioned disadvantages, the combustion mechanism of these fuels have resulted in a lower combustion efficiency. Due to droplet entrainment, many of the droplets are ejected out of the nozzle before complete combustion. Properties of liquefying fuels have also led to mechanical and structural issues (Veale *et al.*, 2017).

To this date, there have been many attempts to increase the regression rate of a hybrid rocket engine. From previous research, it is apparent that many factors have a significant impact on the regression rate of one's engine. However, there has yet to be a study which focuses on the pure regression rate of non-liquefying fuels under the absence of chamber pressure. Thus, the paper sets out to compare the regression rate of fuel at atmospheric pressure to determine if it can serve as a future basis for regression rates comparison.

1.2. Background Theory

Regression rate is defined as the rate at which the fuel surface recedes over time, often measured in mm/s. This regression rate for non-liquefying fuels is generally characterized by properties of the boundary layer and the diffusion flame inside the port (Atkinson *et al.*, 2022). This boundary layer is caused by the interaction between the oxidizer flow and the port surface, where the no-slip condition at the fuel surface propagates lower

velocities outwards through fluid viscosity and creates a flow pattern described by the velocity profile (Atkinson *et al.*, 2022).

In the process of combustion, heat is transferred from the diffusion flame to the fuel surface through convection and radiation. Marxman, Wooldridge, and Muzzy has shown that the regression rate of a non-liquifying system can be primarily determined by the convective heat transfer component (Marxman *et al.*, 1964). Shown in Figure 1, The primary phenomenon which hinders the convective heat transfer and thus the performance of a hybrid rocket engine is widely known as the blowing effect. As the fuel undergoes sublimation in the combustion chamber, fuel ablates perpendicularly to the flow of the oxidizer (Atkinson *et al.*, 2022). Moving down the port, this process is accentuated by the continuous addition of fuel into the stream, the further development of the flow field, and increases in flame height (Nguyen & Thomas, 2023). These factors inhibit the combustion and result in a reduced heat flux, leading to a lower regression rate.

Figure 1: Conventional Hybrid Combustion Mechanism

It can be then shown that the flame height from the fuel surface has a direct effect on the convective heat transfer, as the flame height positively impacts the blowing effect, commonly expressed through the blowing coefficient. Where this distance is seen to be in the range of several micrometers, this distance is believed to be larger by magnitudes for hybrid engines (Shimida *et al.*, 2012). With these considerations, Marxman's diffusion-limited theory was developed, showing the relationship between mass flux and regression rate for a fuel slab submerged in oxidizer as seen in Equation (1) (Marxman *et al.*, 1964):

$$\rho_f \dot{r} = 0.036 \frac{G_x^{-0.2}}{\mu_x} B^{0.23} \quad (1)$$

Where G is the local combined mass flux, x is the position along the port and B is the blowing coefficient. This model was later parameterized and converted to a space-time averaged form as (Marxman *et al.*, 1964):

$$\dot{r} = \alpha G^n \quad (2)$$

1.3. Geometric Consideration

The instantaneous port geometry can be calculated based on the mass measured experimentally by considering a fuel grain with a homogeneous density as a cylindrical port, where r_o is the radius of the fuel grain and r_i is the port radius. The fuel volume can then be given as Equation (3) which can be rewritten in terms of port diameter as seen in Equation (4):

$$V = \pi r_o^2 L - r_i^2 = \frac{m}{\rho_f} \quad (3)$$

$$d_i = \sqrt{d_o^2 - \frac{4m}{L\pi\rho_f}} \quad (4)$$

2. Methods

2.1. Experimental Setup

To perform the experiment, an entire setup of a hybrid motor was constructed from scratch. The motor and propellant feed system (PFS) was designed to take into consideration a few requirements, namely the measurement of oxidizer mass flow rate and the static and dynamic pressure of the PFS. The system can be divided into 3 categories: ignition, pneumatics, and pressure system. The propellant feed system is illustrated in Figure 2. The combustion process takes place in the combustion chamber (the fuel grain itself) connected to the pressure system which facilitates the flow of gaseous oxygen. On the other hand, the pneumatic system comprises two pneumatic ball valves (main and low flow). Whereas the main valve is designed to provide the designed oxidizer mass flow rate for combustion, the low flow valve provides a lower oxidizer flow rate for ignition. The flow rate in the low flow segment was adjusted using a needle valve. These pneumatic valves are controlled through solenoid valves utilizing compressed air fed by the air compressor. The use of solenoid valves allows actuation of pneumatic valves from a distance. The ignition system used in this setup features the use of nichrome wires, a match, a 12-volt battery, and an Arduino relay module.

2.2. Cold Flow: Predicting Oxidizer Mass Flow Rate

To measure the oxidizer flow rate of the system during a burn, a scale should be used to measure the change in mass of the oxygen cylinder. However, as the cylinder weighs greater than a hundred kilograms, the precision of the scale was simply not sufficient for the data this experiment aims to collect. Thus, an entirely separate experiment was conducted to predict the oxidizer mass flow rate at pressures within the operating interval of the system. This experiment was referred to as cold flow - the testing of the system's oxidizer flow rate in the absence of any combustion process. To determine the relationship between the measured dynamic pressure of the system and the oxidizer mass flow rate, the cylinder was set to a certain pressure and the main valve was actuated for 10-20 seconds depending on the relative pressure of the trial tested. The cold flow extended the time that the main valve was on to acquire a greater change in mass. Quantitatively, it was evident that the oxidizer mass flow rate was lower at lower pressures, requiring an additional 10 seconds to retain the same precision.

A total of 97 trials were conducted. It was observed that there exists a linear relationship between dynamic pressure and the oxidizer mass flow rate. Using the linear model, the oxidizer mass flow rate for each trial is

then predicted and used in calculations for trials of the hotfire experiments. The obtained linear model is as follows:

$$\dot{m}_{gox} = 0.6451 P_{dynamic} + 0.1166 \quad (5)$$

Figure 2: Experimental Apparatus

2.3. Ground Static Hot-Fires

Using gaseous oxygen as the oxidizer, hot fires were conducted using 3 types of fuel: High-density polyethylene (HDPE), Polypropylene (PP), and Polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA). As oxidizer mass flux is a function of port area and oxidizer mass flow rate, several burns were able to be conducted using one same fuel grain as port diameter change after each burn. 6 fuel grains were used to conduct the experiment with a total number of 53 trials. It should be noted that the number of trials for one fuel grain differ from one to another due to ignition failures. Each fuel grain had identical initial dimensions of 12cm, 6cm, and 1cm in length, outer diameter, and port diameter.

Before hotfire procedures, the initial mass and dimensions of the fuel grain were measured. The procedure for a hotfire is as follows: First, the pressure regulator is adjusted to the desired pressure. Then, the ball valve is switched off and the needle valve is turned on. The static pressure is then recorded. Once the steps are

completed and initial dimensions of the fuel are measured, ignition is set up. A camera is then installed in front of the pressure display for dynamic pressure and the ball valve is switched back on. The needle valve is adjusted to the extent where there is only a low continuous flow of oxygen enough to keep the ignition match burning. Once the site is evacuated, the timer relays are set to 5 seconds for low flow (low oxidizer flow rate to facilitate ignition), and 5 seconds for the main flow with a 5 second delay controlled by an Arduino relay module. Once the combustion is complete, the fuel grain is removed from the securing pieces to measure its final mass. The video is also processed for its dynamic pressure during the hotfire to predict the corresponding oxidizer flow rate for the current trial. The steps were repeated for all of the hotfires conducted for this experiment.

2.4. Data Processing and Correction

The fuel grain masses before and after each trial is used to find the space-averaged port diameter using Equation (4). As regression rate is the derivative of radius in respect to time, average regression rate is estimated as the change in diameter over burn time for each trial. Oxidizer mass flux is calculated using the predicted flow rate and the port area calculated using the average port diameter (final and initial inner), estimated as Equation (6):

$$\dot{r}_i \approx \frac{d_f - d_i}{2t_b} \quad (6)$$

It can be shown that the diameter is the best choice of spatial time-dependent variable to average over time with this method as it leads to the least theoretical error in the calculated oxidizer flux (Karabeyoglu *et al.*, 2007). Oxidizer mass flux and regression rate can then be linearized using a logarithmic graph, where a and n are obtained based on the slope and y-intercept of the graph. For this paper, these parameters are obtained for an oxidizer flux measured in standard international units and a regression rate measured in millimeters per second. A method for correcting the systematic error in regression rate calculations due to regression rate's nonlinear evolution over axial distance and time was also tried. The method was developed by Karabeyoglu, Cantwell, and Zilliac, and uses an iterative process based on the relationship between the oxidizer to fuel mass flow rate ratio to the regression rate, and has shown capacity to reduce data scatter in some tests (Karabeyoglu *et al.*, 2007). In the study, MATLAB was used to implement the method. As fuel mass flow rate can be an indicator of an outlier, it was calculated for every trial conducted. The time-averaged mass flow rate of the fuel was taken as the change in fuel mass over burn time. This rate should increase over time, and if the data collected does not match the trend caution was taken with the data.

3. Results

3.1. Raw Regression Results

In total, 3 high-density polyethylene, 2 polypropylene, and 1 polymethyl methacrylate fuel grains were burned in gaseous oxygen to obtain regression rates as a function of oxidizer mass flux. As the paper focuses on the regression rates of non-liquefying fuels at atmospheric pressure, trials were conducted without a nozzle. The oxidizer mass flux ranges for HDPE varied within 20 to 190 $kgm^{-2}s^{-1}$, PP from 20 to 180 $kgm^{-2}s^{-1}$, and PMMA from 20 to 100 $kgm^{-2}s^{-1}$ shown in their respective orders in Equation (6), Equation (7), and Equation (8). Applying the power fit to each set of data, the following regression rate equations are obtained for each fuel without O/F correction. The unit mms^{-1} was used as it is the most common practice in regression rate studies in hybrid propulsion.

$$r = 0.0290 (G)^{0.508} \quad (6)$$

$$r = 0.0484 (G)^{0.391} \quad (7)$$

$$r = 0.0354 (G)^{0.454} \quad (8)$$

3.2. Results with Regression Rate Correction

The application of the regression rate correction method did not visibly reduce data scattering graphically, while the RMSE of the best fit model does not change significantly, except for PMMA where it dropped by 50.19%. This could be explained by high O/F ratios in the experiments ($O/F > 7$) which reduces the error created when experimentally determining the regression rate. However, the method reduced the p-value by 39.2%, 99.9% and 76.3%, while slightly improving the coefficient of determination r^2 , suggesting that the corrected data is better suited for the mathematical model chosen. Applying the power fit to the corrected data, the fit yields the following regression rate equations for each fuel:

$$r = 0.0320 (G)^{0.493} \quad (9)$$

$$r = 0.0471 (G)^{0.406} \quad (10)$$

$$r = 0.0342 (G)^{0.465} \quad (11)$$

The models of each regression rate model are plotted along with their calculated uncertainties (with propagation of uncertainty) and their respective 95% confidence intervals. Data points outside of our confidence intervals are treated as outliers. The models are shown in **Figure 3**.

Figure 3: Regression Rate Curves of Polypropylene (A), PMMA (B), and High-Density Polyethylene (C)

4. Discussion

4.1. Comparison to Literature Data: PMMA

Figure 4 compares the regression rates of the current study to available regression rate models for PMMA. The regression rate models in the plot are also listed in Table 1 with corresponding oxidizer mass flux ranges and chamber pressures (Pastrone, 2012)(Cai *et al.*, 2013)(Greiner *et al.*, 1992)(Araujo *et al.*, 2017). Discrepancies in the regression rate data are apparent, and that can be attributed to the different conditions in which the engine is operated in. Looking at the table, previous fuel regression rate functions have traditionally been done with a nozzle, hence the varying chamber pressure range for each experiment conducted. Moreover, these regression rate models are also obtained from data over a limited oxidizer mass flux range. Issues arise when these data are used directly for comparison with different systems of fuels, oxidizers and additives or at

different scales. The regression rate of PMMA of the current study is comparatively lower than regression rates under a pressurized chamber as expected. This difference is further exaggerated with increasing oxidizer mass flux ranges.

Figure 4: PMMA Regression Rate Literature Comparison

Table 1: PMMA Regression Rate Models

Study	Regression Rate Characterization				
	Number of Tests	Oxidizer Flux Range	Chamber Pressure (MPa)	a	n
Yasuo et al.	4	10 - 20	0.26 - 4	0.0276	0.5810
Cai et al.	7	90.59 - 152.73	--	0.0165	0.7620
Thais et al.	20	1 - 7	0.3 - 0.6	0.0499	0.5344
Karabeyoglu et al.	8	33 - 26.6	0.3 - 2.6	0.0870	0.6150

4.2. Comparison to Literature Data: HDPE

The same phenomena can be observed in the regression rate model comparisons of HDPE motors in Figure 5. The models are listed in Table 2. As expected, all other experimental models predicted higher regression rates. The models seem to predict higher regression rates in the order of their experiments' chamber pressure ranges. The discrepancy between this study's results and results of Alessandro and Barato despite covering a similar range of oxidizer flux, combined with the similarity between the other two models and this paper's model despite the data covering different ranges of oxidizer flux, suggests that chamber pressure range is the primary

factor in distinguishing these models (Alessandro & Barato, 2023)(Karabeyoglu *et al.*, 2005). Specifically, Lee, S. Kim, J. Kim, and Moon’s model is very close to this test’s model at the beginning of their oxidizer flux collection range or extrapolating to lower flux values, but the difference between the two models grows to a significant degree as oxidizer flux increases (Lee *et al.*, 2015). This can be explained from their chamber pressure being increasing from 2.7 bars, a value comparatively close to our testing conditions, at a flux of $87.56\text{ kg/m}^2\text{ s}$, up to 12.8 bars at its maximum flux of $303.68\text{ kg/m}^2\text{ s}$, assuming chamber pressure increases positively to oxidizer flux. This suggests that higher pressure difference leads to higher local discrepancy between the models.

Figure 5: HDPE Regression Rate Literature Comparison

Table 2: HDPE Regression Rate Models

Study	Regression Rate Characterization				
	Number of Tests	Oxidizer Flux Range	Chamber Pressure (MPa)	a	n
Alessandro et al.	21	18.77 - 126.0	0.957 - 2.500	0.1245	0.3722
Lee et al.	20	87.56 - 303.63	0.27 - 1.28	0.0291	0.5270
Karabeyoglu et al.	4	77 - 261	0.72 - 1.25	0.0489	0.4688

4.3. Error Analysis

2 outliers were determined for the HDPE data, 0 for PMMA and 1 for PP. The existence of these outliers is likely attributed to the unreliable ignition system used, which may not light up all of the port in some cases and

may preheat the port differently between trials. The RMSE for the polypropylene experiments was 11.27% of the lowest corrected regression rate, which indicates a relatively low amount of error. For PMMA the percentage is 2.253%, although the low number of trials makes it difficult to judge the amount of error in the experiment. Lastly for HDPE the RMSE ranges from 7.261% to 21.64% of the regression rate, indicating a high amount of error. It should be noted that the RMSE seems to go up the more fuel grains tested, where 1 PMMA fuel grain, 2 PPE fuel grains and 3 HDPE fuel grains were burned, indicating there may be inconsistencies between fuel grains causing random error. The RMSE for the polypropylene experiments was 11.27% of the lowest corrected regression rate, which indicates a relatively low amount of error. For PMMA the percentage is 2.253%, although the low number of trials makes it difficult to judge the amount of error in the experiment. Lastly for HDPE the RMSE ranges from 7.261% to 21.64% of the regression rate, indicating a high amount of error. It should be noted that the RMSE seems to go up the more fuel grains tested, where 1 PMMA fuel grain, 2 PPE fuel grains and 3 HDPE fuel grains were burned, indicating there may be inconsistencies between fuel grains causing random error. A compiled figure of residuals of each fuel can be seen in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Residuals of Polypropylene (A), PMMA (B), and High-Density Polyethylene (C)

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, it appears that the regression rates of traditional hybrid fuels without a pressurized combustion chamber tend to be lower. This is consistent in our experimental results when in comparison to other studies in the previous section. This research provides insight into the importance of pure regression rate databases when evaluating fuels regardless of liquefying or not. While previous papers have established the regression rates of traditional polymeric fuels, often these data cannot be used for direct comparison as the database tends to be created for the optimization of one specific engine and cannot be generalized from one setup to another. This can vary significantly as regression rate enhancement techniques such as swirling injectors can already increase the regression rate of a polymeric fuel by 3 folds, hence why many available models were also neglected in comparison.

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Author Biography

1st Chen Szu Heng– Project leader of hybrid propulsion research entity, Amateur Experimental Rocketry Dhaka (AERD) under the research grant provided by the American International University of Bangladesh, which tested Bangladesh’s first hybrid rocket engine. He is also currently a propulsion member of Taiwan’s Advanced Rocket Research Center (ARRC), the first organization to achieve hovering with a hybrid-based propulsion system, and the Student Society of Taiwan Advanced Rocketry (STAR), a joint university initiative to create a student-made monopropellant-based hover vehicle.

2nd Emmy Cai – Member of Amateur Experimental Rocketry Dhaka (AERD).